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Review Article

Herbal Face Toner - Nature Touch Skin Care

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ABSTRACT

Herbal Cosmetics are safe, fewer adverse effects, and wider market acceptance, natural medicines are becoming more and more popular than artificial formulations. The creation and assessment of a topical drug delivery system are the main objectives of this project, which highlights the natural components long-lasting and precise activity. Using natural components including aloe vera, neem, papaya, tulsi, and amla, the study seeks to create a herbal face toner with astringent, relaxing, and soothing properties. To ensure its effectiveness and safety, the toner's physicochemical characteristics such as stability, pH, and surface tension are evaluated. Because they are non-toxic and less likely to cause allergic responses, herbal cosmetics are becoming more and more popular. This study concludes with a thorough analysis of face toners, including their formulation procedures, modes of action, and dermatological advantages.

INTRODUCTION

The Greek term "kosm-tikos," which means possessing strength, order, and decorating ability, is where the word "cosmetic" originated. Lifestyle, routines, climate, and upkeep are some of the elements that affect the health of skin and hair. In Summer time heat waves can cause dryness of the skin, which can result in sunburns, wrinkles, freckles, pimples, and pigmentation. In a similar vein, severe winter weather can cause infections, hair loss, maceration, wounds, and skin splits.¹ All age groups are susceptible to skin illnesses, which

are frequently brought on by chemical agents, environmental pollutants, microbial exposure, and, to a lesser degree, malnutrition.² The ancient discipline of Ayurveda has used natural plants and herbs to create cosmetics that improve appearance and shield the skin from harm.³

Cosmetic – Articles intended to be rubbed, poured, powdered or sprayed on, introduces into or otherwise applied to the human body or any part of the body there of for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance.⁴

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Herbal Cosmetics - Herbal cosmetics are preparations made with phytochemicals derived from a range of botanical sources that affect skin function and supply nutrients essential for a healthy body and skin. Herbal cosmetics are made from natural herbs and their products or extracts that are used for their fragrant qualities in cosmetic preparation.⁵ Because of their accessibility, potency, and minimal toxicity, herbal products are in great demand. The expanding demand for cosmeceuticals, which is fueled by the desire for youthful and appealing appearances, is in line with the increased usage of herbal substances in cosmetics.⁶

Need of Cosmetic

- To improve overall appearance.
- Reduce skin flaws.
- Use in psychology.
- Application in social.
- Use in healthcare.
- Skin protection against dust, UV radiation, and harsh weather.
- Effect of cleaning.
- Emollient action.⁷

Herbal Cosmetics For Various Types of Skin

1. For Dry Skin

Example of Herbs :- Rubia Cardifolia (Manjistha), Triphala, Tulsi, Glycerihza glabra in sesame oil.

Fruit face mask

Banana or avocado pulp.

2. For Sensitive Skin

Example of Herbs :- Usheero, Curcuma longa, Triphala, Azadircta indica mustaka, Nimba in coconut oil.

Fruit face mask

Banana or pineapple pulp.

3. For Oily Skin

Example of Herbs :- Tulsi, Idhora, Nimba, Curcuma longa.

Fruit face mask

Strawberry or papaya pulp.¹

Herbal Cosmetics are maintained in effective manner with following Benefits :-

1. They don't induce allergic reactions and have no negative side effects.
2. They easily mix in with hair and skin.
3. When used in little quantities, these are far more effective than other cosmetics.
4. Cosmetics blow bulk properties are reduced by the plant extract, which also has the appropriate pharmacological impact.
5. Accessible and available in a variety of plans.
6. Their herbal ingredients are more stable, pure, and effective.
7. Easy to produce.
8. Herbal cosmetics are easier to use and keep for a longer period of time.
9. Cheap.⁸

Herbal face toner :-

A toner is a water-based liquid that contains active ingredients to cleanse the skin, maintain a stable pH, reduce pores, and give the skin an instant glow. It gets rid of the debris and pollutants that are lodged in your skin's pores before you wash your face. When incorporated into a regular skin care regimen, it has a significant favorable effect on the appearance of aging skin. It moisturizes the skin because of its antioxidant properties.

Types of Toner :-

1. Skin fresheners or bracers: - It is the toner's mild form. The toner contains glycerine (a humectant) and water. Humectants hydrate the epidermis. The most well-known example of it is Rosewater. Normal, dehydrated, and sensitive skin types are best suited for it.

2. Skin tonics: - Skin tonics are typically stronger and contain water, a humectant component, and a small amount of alcohol (up to 20%). Orange flower water is an excellent example of a skin tonic. Oily skin can be treated with skin tonics.

3. Acid toner: - They are a potent type of toner that usually contains beta or alpha hydroxy acids. The three alpha hydroxy acids that are most

frequently used to exfoliate the skin's surface are glycolic, lactic, and Mandelic acids. The most widely utilized beta hydroxy acid that is most effective at exfoliating the skin's deeper layers is salicylic acid.

4. Astringents :- The strongest type of toner is an astringent, which has a high alcohol content (20–60%), water, antiseptics, and a humectant. Because they can remove excess protective lipids from the skin when they utilize a lot of alcohol, these can be harmful and irritating to the skin.

Advantages of Skin Toner :-

- 1 Toners remove these leftover pollutants to give your face another thorough cleansing.
2. Regular use of the toner helps reduce the appearance of pores.
3. Toners are useful for restoring the skin's pH equilibrium.
4. Toner tends to absorb fast into the skin, providing an immediate moisture boost.
5. Toners can provide an immediate sense of renewal to your skin.
6. Toners are water-based liquids that have anti-inflammatory and relaxing properties that can help stop breakouts and infections. They are essential for avoiding skin infections.
7. A toner gives your skin an extra layer of defense. Among other environmental stressors, it acts as a barrier against dirt, dust, smog, and sunlight.
8. Toners are a mixture of ingredients used to treat a range of skin conditions.
9. Toners are for oily or acne-prone skin.

Disadvantages of skin Toner: -

1. Toners that include alcohol make the skin flaky and dry.
2. It may cause skin irritation if overused. For example, redness and edema.⁹

Direction to use: -

1. Mist your hands or face after washing them.
2. On the face or surface of the hands, let the spray sit for a while.

3. Use a cloth or soft cotton to wipe away the spray.

4. To improve skin rejuvenation, use the toner twice daily.¹⁰

Application Technique of Toner :-

1. Cotton Pad Method

- Apply toner to a cotton pad.
- Sweep gently over the neck and face.
- No rinsing required.

2. Spritz Method

- Directly mist the face and neck with toner.
- Use your hands to gently pat dry.
- Ideal for skin that is sensitive or dry.

3. Gauze Method

- Use toner to soak the gauze.
- Sweep gently over the neck and face.
- efficient at cleaning and exfoliating pores.

4. Sweep and Pat Method

- Use toner to soak the cotton pad.
- Sweep upward across the face.
- Use your hands to pat dry.

5. Tap and Glow Method

- Use toner to soak the cotton pad.
- Tap lightly on the neck and face.
- facilitates hydration and absorption.

How to utilise it :-

1. Be sure to shake well before using.
2. Mist your face with toner after washing it.
3. Give the spray time to settle on your face.
4. To remove the toner, use cotton or a soft cloth.
5. For better skin-rejuvenating results, use the toner twice a day.¹¹

□ Literature Review

1) M. Safitri *et al.* (2024) :- The goal of the study is to find an appropriate formulation for a facial toner extract that demonstrates favorable physical characteristics as assessed by hedonic, pH, homogeneity, and organoleptic tests. The current work used an experimental strategy to use a 70% ethanol solvent in the maceration procedure to create a 70% ethanol extract of cucumber fruit. Because cucumbers are abundant in water, vitamin

C, and antioxidants and low in alcohol, the researchers chose to use them as their ingredient. Cucumbers are the perfect choice for revitalizing facial skin because of these qualities. Improving efficiency and cost-effectiveness is another goal of using herbal toners. The purpose of phytochemical screening is to identify the secondary metabolite chemicals present in the 70% ethanol extract of cucumber fruit and the simplicia of cucumber peel.¹²

2) L. T. Fadila *et al.* (2024) :- The aim of this study was to ascertain the physical characteristics of essential oil toner preparations made from bay leaf plants (*Syzygium polyanthum*) and to comprehend the effectiveness of these preparations as an acne treatment against *Propionibacterium acnes*. A study by Kun Harismah and Chusniatun (2017) found that 0.2% essential oil is present in bay leaves (*Syzygium polyanthum*). Bay leaves (*Syzygium polyanthum*) were extracted using 70% ethanol, and the results demonstrated efficacy against *Candida albicans*. The study's materials were 15 kg of bay leaves (*Syzygium polyanthum*) that were sourced from Banjara City's Purwaha District.¹³

3) S. S. Dash *et al.* (2024) :- Their goal was to assess how well-known toners worked against face isolates in terms of antibacterial activity. Bacteria were extracted from ten people's faces for this investigation, and they were identified in part by biochemical, microscopic, and cultural studies. The purpose of this study was to assess the antimicrobial qualities of several face toners on the market in relation to the bacteria found on human face skin. In general, facial toner is the step in between skincare products. It should be applied before to using a moisturizer but after washing the face. In the past, following cleansing with an alkaline soap product, toners were used to restore the skin's pH balance.¹⁴

4) A. F. Ely *et al.* (2023) :- This study sought to create a green tea kombucha face toner with good

physical stability and anti-acne properties. There was experimental research in this study. Face toner's antimicrobial ingredients served as the research population. Green tea was chosen as the primary raw material for this investigation because it is less expensive to buy and has a catechin level that is similar to white tea. Kombucha green tea leaves, the active ingredient in this study, were fermented for 14 days and tested using the pH and Diameter of Inhibition Zone (DIZ) methods.¹⁵

5) M. parbhane *et al.* (2022) :- The major objective of creating a herbal face toner is to keep the skin tonic. Numerous herbal face toners are on the market, and some of them have negative side effects including redness and itching. *Convolvulus prostratus* extract, which has anti-inflammatory qualities, aloe vera gel, which has anti-fungal qualities, and glycerine, which has lubricating qualities, were used in an attempt to create a herbal face toner for your skin. Herbal face toner is evaluated based on a number of criteria, including color, scent, pH, skin irritation testing, and antimicrobial action.¹⁶

6) N. R. Windayani *et al.* (2021) :- This article focuses on developing and assessing Face wrinkles and hyperpigmentation are two of the many types of facial skin that can be problematic for mothers with dry skin. Because they are easier to manufacture and contain less sugar than other varieties of dates, ajwa dates are used to make toners. the goal of studies on vitamin C and antioxidants in date water toner products, as well as the evaluation of date water toner for dry facial skin using clinical trials, preference tests, and sensory evaluations. The experimental approach is the one that is employed.¹⁷

7) P. Meetham *et al.* (2017) :- In this study, ten individuals had their senses evaluated using base formulas that stabilized after accelerated assessments. The base containing glycerin, panthenol, and hydroxyethyl cellulose (a total of 3.6%) was further developed to green tea

preparations and showed a considerable ($p < 0.05$) preference ($82.3 \pm 0.55\%$) over the others. A facial condition known as "oily skin" is typically defined as one that is greasy, heavy, and shiny as a result of excessive sebum production and secretion.¹⁸

❑ **AIM:** - Herbal Face Toner – Nature's Touch Skin Care

❑ **Objectives:** -

- Maintaining the tonicity of the skin is the main objective of creating herbal face toner.
- To maintain skin pH balance.
- Additionally, it helps to tighten pores in the skin (anti-aging).
- Reducing annoyance.
- It is applied to promote blood flow.
- Herbal cosmetics are non-toxic and help to alleviate allergic reactions.
- When compared to chemical toners, it has no negative effects.
- Skin hydration is the primary goal of herbal face toner.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

❖ **Azadirachta indica**

Synonyms - Neem

Botanical name - Azadirachta

Family - Meliaceae

Genus - Neem Tree

Chemical constituent - Azadirachtin, nimbolinin, nimbin, nimbidin, nimbidol, sodium nirobinate, gedunin, salannin, and quercetin.

Use-Anti-inflammatory, antihyperglycemic, antiulcer, antimalarial, antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral, antioxidant.

Figure No. 3 - Azadirachta indica

❖ **Aloe Vera**

Synonyms- Aloe indica Royle

Botanical name-Aloe Vera

Family-Liliaceae

Genus-Aloe

Chemical constituent-Anthraquinones, anthrones, chromones, tetrahydroanthracenones, and anthrone/tetrahydroanthracenone glycosides.

Use -Anti- Inflammatory, Reduce Redness, Antioxidant, Antibacterial, Anti-Wrinkle.

Figure No. 4 - Aloe vera

❖ **Carica papaya**

Synonyms - Papaya

Botanical name - Carica Papaya

Family - Caricaceae

Genus - Carica

Chemical constituent-Circle Reduction, Alkaloids, Glycosides, Tannins, Saponins, flavonoids and Glycosides.

Use-Exfoliation, Anti- Inflammatory, Moisturizing, Antioxidant, Wrinkle Reduction, Melasma treatment, Dark .

Figure No. 5 - Carica papaya

❖ **Ocimum sanctum**

Synonyms - Ocimum tenuiflorum,
Botanical name - Ocimum tenuiflorum
Family - Lamiaceae
Genus - Ocimum
Chemical constituent - 0.7% volatile oil comprising about 71% eugenol and 20% methyl eugenol. carvacrol and sesquiterpine hydrocarbon caryophyllene. Two flavonoids orientin and andvicenin.

Use - Antioxidant, anti-acne, anti-ageing, antiseptic properties against rashes, skin conditions. also helpful in lessening acne, pimple, and scar itching, antiviral, antibacterial, and antifungal medications.

Figure No. 6 - Ocimum sanctum

❖ **Embillica officinalis**

Synonyms - Indian gooseberry
Botanical name - Phyllanthus emblica
Family - Phyllanthaceae
Genus - Phyllanthus
Chemical constituent - Gallic acid, chebulic acid, ellagic acid, kaempferol, kaempferol-3-o-glucoside, gallo tannin, and rutin, phosphoric acid, essential oils, linoleic acid, oleic acid, stearic acid, palmitic acid, and mystic acid. The bark of the plant contains proanthocyanidins, tannins, and leucodelphinidin.

Use - Antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal properties, antioxidant. Help enhance girls' skin disorders in the 35–50 age range. minimizes wrinkles, suggesting that amla fruit is a promising option for weight control and antiageing.²

Figure No. 7 - Embillica officinalis

❑ **Extraction of an active constituent from crude drug**

- ✓ Take 25gm powdered plant material in 250ml beaker
- ✓ Add 250ml of distilled water in it
- ✓ Heat for 24 hours
- ✓ Then filter the extract
- ✓ The obtained extract evaporates
- ✓ This extract further uses for the preparation of herbal face toner

Preparation of herbal toner

- ✓ Take the extract of Herb
 - ✓ In a beaker and mix well
 - ✓ Add Perfume Excipient in above mixture
 - ✓ Then add Moisturizer
 - ✓ Add few drops of a preservative
- Makeup the volume with distilled water and mix well.

Exicipients

Exicipients	Function
Glycerin	Moisture, Humectant
Tween 80	Surfactant, Emulsifier
Propylene glycol	Moisturizer, Emulsifier
Di .EDTA	Chelating Agent

PEG-40 Castor Oil	Cleansing, Emulsifying
Mint	Astringent, Anti- microbial
Citric Acid 10%	pH Adjuster
Panthenol	Skin - Conditioning

Evaluation of gel toner

Preliminary evaluation of formulation was carried out as follows.

➤ pH

20 mg of the gel was placed in a beaker, and the pH meter was calibrated and used to measure the pH.

➤ Spreadability Test

Two slides were sandwiched with 500 mg of the gel. A 100g weight was set on the upper slide. Extra gel was scraped off and the weight was taken off. A 20g weight was supplied to the upper slide, which was attached with non-flexible string, while the lower slide was fixed on the apparatus's board. The spread ability was tested and the time it took for the upper slide to slip off was recorded.

➤ Homogeneity

The gel was tested by touching it with the hands.

➤ Appearance

By examining its color, opacity, and other physical characteristics, the created gel's appearance was determined.

➤ After Feel

Properties such as emollient nature, slipperiness, and the amount of gel remained after application were noticed when the herbal gel toner was applied to the skin.

➤ Smear Type

After applying gel to the skin, the test was performed to determine if the resulting smear was aqueous or oily.

➤ Removal

The gel that had been put to the skin was removed by washing it off with tap water while using very little force.

➤ Patch Test

Applying 1-3 grams of the item to be tested to the sensitive area of the skin, such as the skin behind the ears, was done on a piece of cloth or a funnel. One square meter of skin was covered with the cosmetic that was to be examined. Also, control patches were used. The patch site is examined 24 hours later. Since no response was found, the test was conducted three times. Since there was no reaction on the third treatment, the individual might not be considered hypersensitive.

➤ Irritancy Test

The gel was applied to the dorsal side of the left hand at a surface area of 1 square centimeter, and it was checked for oedema, redness, and irritation at equal intervals for 24 hours.

➤ Accelerated Stability Studies

All of the formulations underwent accelerated stability tests, which involved keeping them at room temperature for 20 days at regular intervals. Homogeneity, viscosity, physical changes, pH, and smear type were among the parameters examined during the stability investigations.

➤ Extrudability

This study used a straightforward methodology. After the gel solidified in the container, the formulation was transferred into the collapsible tubes. The formulation's extrudability was assessed by measuring the weight in grams needed to extrude a 0.5 cm gel ribbon in 10 seconds.

➤ Diffusion study

The obtained formulation was subjected to a diffusion study using agar nutrition medium at any concentration. It was put into a petri dish with a hole drilled in the middle, and gel was added. We measured the amount of time it took for the gel to diffuse.⁵

❑ DISCUSSION

There are several benefits to using herbal toners in skincare, such as hydrating skin, lowering pH levels, reducing pore size, and leaving skin feeling renewed. Usually, they are employed to get rid of any last bits of makeup or grime. In the lab, cost-effective methods were employed for both formulation and assessment. Herbal and alcohol-based toners are frequently kinder and more nourishing, which makes them appropriate for a range of skin types, including sensitive skin.

❑ CONCLUSION

The present review focused on the utilized and value of herbal Toner. It contains the awareness and for cosmetics with herbal ingredients as it strongly felt that the herbal product is safe and free from adverse effect. A toner is a skin care solution that has a number of components, including a cleansing agent, a pH balancer, hydration, refreshing, and calming properties. dirt or oil remover, occasionally an antifungal or antibacterial chemical, etc. It has been observed that certain agents have adverse effects, such as skin redness, irritation, and itching. Therefore, a chemical-free toner must be created, using a herbal extract instead, which may be the ideal substitute for chemical-based toner. Along with other necessary ingredients, the designed toner includes herbal extracts of neem, amala, alovera, and fenugreek. A number of tests, including visual inspection, pH, appearance, the spreadability test, and a diffusion research, were then used to assess the formulation. The herbal toner has positive qualities. It is feasible to create

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